

TRANSFORM

Lombardy needs from citizens' voices

Report of the survey conducted within the
EU H2020 TRANSFORM project

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TRANSFORM

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Regione
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Abstract

This report presents the results of a survey conducted in April 2021 in which a sample of one thousand citizens residing in Lombardy expressed their opinions on research and innovation needs for their territory. The survey is one of the components of a broader participatory process organized by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation along with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda. The consultation took place within the framework of the European project TRANSFORM, which aims to design and test pathways to involve the citizens in the regional research and innovation governance.

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Research and Innovation citizens' needs in Lombardy

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Introduction

Every three years, the Lombardy Region designs a strategic document that defines regional research and innovation priorities (the **Three-Year Strategic Program for Research, Innovation, and Technology Transfer**). Citizens' needs have been at the basis of this strategy since its inception, but thanks to TRANSFORM - a European project coordinated by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation - for the first time, regional needs have been identified directly from citizens. In April 2021, around 1,000 people living in Lombardy participated in a survey on regional needs and priorities for research and innovation, which were then included in the Three-Year Strategic Program for 2021-2023. The survey was part of a process aiming to engage the citizens more broadly and to make regional research and innovation governance more open, inclusive, and participatory.

of residence. Additional details on other sociodemographic factors were also collected, such as the area of origin (rural, urban, suburban), the number of family members, and the presence of young, elderly, or dependent persons in the family. The survey - composed of 15 questions - was administered by an agency specializing in polls and opinion research (SWG) between the 20th and the 28th of April, both online and via telephone, to enable people with different habits and digital skills to participate.

Figure 1 - Sample composition: age

Figure 2 - Sample composition: gender

The survey and who responded to it

A total of 1,002 citizens, over 18 and being residents in Lombardy, responded to the questionnaire, which has developed by Giannino Bassetti Foundation along with the Lombardy Region and Finlombarda. The respondents were selected to be as representative as possible of the Lombardy population and were balanced by age, gender, and province

The designers, the commissioning public authority, and the funder

The questionnaire was developed by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation, the coordinating entity of the TRANSFORM project, along with the Lombardy Region and Finlombarda. The data were analysed by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation and the resulting report was delivered to the Directorate General Education, University, Research, Innovation, and Simplification of the Lombardy Region. The results that emerged from the survey were also used to design the next step

of the TRANSFORM participatory process, a deliberative workshop dedicated to the topic of the fair energy transition in Lombardy. The survey was developed and administered within the TRANSFORM project timeframe. TRANSFORM has been funded by the European Commission under the H2020 Framework Program.

The results

Citizens' objectives in Lombardy

In the first block of questions, participants were asked to indicate what are their priorities for the Lombardy territory, starting from a list developed by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation and based on the most relevant goals identified at the regional and international levels (also

Figure 3 - Sample composition: province of residence

relying on the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations).

When answering the question “How much each of the objectives listed is an objective for the Lombardy territory and its citizens?” participants could respond “Very much,” “Much,” “Partially,” “A little,” “Not at all.” All the listed objectives were found to be urgent, but citizens identified three priorities:

1. More children and young people with high quality education (66%)
2. More people with decent jobs (65%)
3. Less cities' impact on pollution (62%)

Citizens' answers also revealed that the youngest (18-24 years old) and - to some extent - senior people (over 65) prioritize objectives that are more directly related to environmental sustainability¹. Citizens were invited to reflect on if and how the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted on the objectives listed below. According to the respondents, the three areas most affected by the pandemic are **education, health, and job**. Overall, the impact of COVID is highlighted most strongly by people with large families

Figure 4 - Goals for the Lombardy territory: “Very much” and “Much” answers

¹ List of objectives considered related to the theme ‘sustainability’: More responsible consumption and production; Better mobility infrastructure; More people using clean and safe water for food and personal care; More actions to protect biodiversity; More people who have access to clean energy at sustainable prices; More actions to fight climate change; Less cities' impact on pollution.

Citizens' priorities in Lombardy

When required to select only two priority objectives, citizens have suggested **work, health, education, and the fight against poverty** (see Figures 5 and 6), with few differences concerning some factors.

For example, when choosing the first priority, citizens belonging to larger families (more than four persons) consider more the need for "Gender equality" (with +9 percentage points compared to the average) and the need for "More people living in health and well-being" (with +7 percentage points above the average). When choosing the second most urgent need, people living in suburban areas selected the following

more often: "More people living in health and well-being" and "More people having access to clean energy at sustainable prices" (with respectively +22 and +16 percentage points compared to the average). Similarly, the need for "More children and young people with high quality education" is more present in families of more than four persons (+9 percentage points compared to the average).

Figure 5 – Citizens' priorities in Lombardy: first choice

Figure 6 - Citizens' priorities in Lombardy: second choice

Responses to the Lombardy territory priorities

But how to respond to the identified priorities? According to citizens, the

solution lies above all in improving public policies and public services and in listening to and involving citizens (see Figures 7 and 8).

Figure 7 - Responses "Very much" and "Much" on actions to address the first priority according to the Lombardy citizens (respondent base 910).

Figure 8 - Responses "Very much" and "Much" on actions to address to the second priority according to Lombardy citizens (respondent base 874).

Lombardy citizens' most urgent needs

The second part of the questionnaire focused on citizens' personal and family needs. When asked to identify a series of needs as essential ("Yes" or "No"), the participants responded as follows (value in percentage of those who answered "Yes"):

1. Preventing illness (87%)
2. Living in safe environments (85%)
3. - Having user-friendly citizen services (e.g., registry office, school enrolment, medical booking) (83%)

- Moving on safe roads (as a pedestrian, cyclist motorist) (83%)

When asked to identify **two priority needs**, participants emphasised the importance of **health (prevention and territorial health)**, **work**, and **safety** by responding as in Figure 9.

Figure 9 - Citizens' personal and family needs priorities (sum of first and second needs)

The graph shows that the rate of citizens who think that research and innovation (public, private, or resulting from public-private collaborations) can meet the priority needs identified are high (between 56% and 49%). However, they are lower than the percentages obtained by other solutions and actions, considered more relevant, such as **public regional and national/international policies** and **involvement of citizens**, but also improvement of people's lifestyles and reliable public information. This is because, in line with several studies, responding to society's challenges cannot be met solely by scientific or technological solutions. Other dimensions (such as social, political, and economic issues, etc.) must also be taken into account.

Finally, listening to and involvement of citizens are indicated as particularly important by a very high percentage of participants to meet the challenges of **environmental sustainability**:

- More responsible consumption and production (83%)
- More actions to protect biodiversity (83%)
- More people using clean and safe water (79%)
- More people who have access to clean energy (77%)

Research and innovation as tools to respond to Lombardy citizens' needs

In the context of personal and family needs, it was asked whether research and innovation could contribute to responding to the needs identified as priorities. According to the participants, research and innovation can provide answers or partial answers to the identified needs (percentages around 67.5% and 24%, respectively).

Research and innovation are identified as potentially relevant solutions, especially in the **medical field**, namely to “Preventing diseases” (no answer “no”), “Receiving timely and appropriate care close to home,” and “Receiving innovative treatments and therapies.” Within the context of **services**, research

and innovation could be applied as solutions for “Using efficient and non-polluting public transport” and “Having user-friendly citizen services (e.g., registry office, school enrolment, medical booking).” In the area of **culture and information**, they may be helpful in “Stimulating personal flourishing through culture and art” and “Access to quality information”. Where research and innovation are identified as essential tools to meet the needs of the territory, the main reasons are that they attract “both public and private investment and resources to meet that need” (35%) and that they provide “concrete answers and/or solutions to that need” (see Figure 10).

- By attracting both public and private investment and resources to meet that need
- By providing concrete answers and/or solutions to that need
- By increasing the level of knowledge and understanding to respond to that need
- By providing data and information that can be useful for policymakers
- Other

Figure 10 - How can research and innovation provide answers to identified needs?

- Because responding to the need requires better public policies (e.g., laws, strategic plans, sanctions, incentives)
- Because a technological response alone would not fully solve the problem
- Because responding to the need requires better citizens' behaviours and/or lifestyles
- Because meeting the need requires better public services (social services, mobility services, etc.)
- Because research and innovation have nothing to do with this need
- Other

Figure 11 - Why can't research and innovation provide answers to identified needs?

Where **technology** is identified as only partially solving or not resolving the needs of citizens, the reasons given by the participants are described as in Figure 11.

Designing research and innovation policies: Actors to be involved

Finally, in the last section of the questionnaire, citizens were asked with whom Lombardy Region should dialogue to define its research and innovation policies. **Universities and research centres (43%), national government (40%), and citizens (37%)** were identified as the primary interlocutors (see also Figure 12).

Figure 12 - With whom should Lombardy Region dialogue to define its research and innovation policies?

Appendix - The Survey Text

Introduction

The following survey, administered to a representative sample of the Lombardy population, aims to identify the needs of Lombardy citizens. Its answers will help the Lombardy Region define research and innovation policies that could contribute to finding solutions to the identified needs.

The survey is part of the [TRANSFORM project](#), financed by the European Commission and coordinated by the [Bassetti Foundation](#). We thank you for your availability and for the answers you will provide.

SECTION I - GENERAL INFORMATION

1. How would you describe the area where you live and spend most of your time?

Answers:

- Urban area
- Suburban area (outside a city)
- Rural area (countryside or small town)
- None of these
- I prefer not to answer
- I don't know

2. How many people live in your house, including yourself?

Answers:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- More than 4
- I prefer not to answer

If the answer is more than 1:

2b) Among the people living in your house, are there people over 70?

Answers:

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

2c)) Among the people living in your house, are there people under 14?

Answers:

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

2d) Among the people living in your house, are there, including you, one or more dependent persons?

Answers:

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

-

SECTION II - THE NEEDS OF THE LOMBARDY TERRITORY

3. We list some objectives. How much is each of them an objective for the Lombardy territory and its citizens?

Answers: *Very much, Much, Partially, A little, Not at all, I don't know.*

- Fewer people in absolute poverty
- More people getting enough food on a regular basis
- More people accessing quality food
- More people living in health and well-being (in terms of health)
- More children and young people with high quality education
- Gender equality (e.g., women that can hold important positions in companies or institutions as well as men; women who receive a salary equal to that of their male colleagues at the same level)
- More people using clean and safe water for food and personal care
- More people who have access to clean energy (for heating, for preparing food, for cooling) at sustainable prices
- More people with decent jobs
- Better mobility infrastructure (railways, roads, etc.)
- More and better services to support marginalised or disadvantaged groups (e.g., people with physical or mental disabilities, immigrants)
- Less cities' impact on pollution
- More responsible consumption and production (to avoid waste and the release of pollutants)
- More actions to fight climate change
- More actions for the protection of biodiversity (conservation of different species of plants and animals in the area)

4. We list the objectives you have previously identified concerning the Lombardy territory and its citizens. For each of them, please indicate whether, in your opinion, they have been turned into more urgent ones by COVID-19.

The interviewer lists the answers that received "Very much/Much" in question 3. For each sentence, the interviewer asks to indicate the impact of COVID with responses "Yes," "No," and "I don't know."

5. Of the objectives identified, which are the TWO most important in the immediate future for the Lombardy territory and its citizens? How would you rank them in order of priority (1st, 2nd)?

The interviewer lists the answers that received "Very much/Much" in question 3.

6. We list some actions below. How much would each contribute to achieving the objective (*insert/cite the first objective by priority*)?

Answers: Very much, Much, Partially, A little, Not at all, I don't know.

- Results and solutions from public research
- Results and solutions from innovation through private companies
- Results and solutions from public research in collaboration with private companies
- Better public services (social services, mobility services, etc.)
- Better regional public policies (laws, sanctions, incentives)
- Better national or international public policies
- Change in people's behaviour and lifestyle
- Reliable public information
- Data from public institutions, which are reliable and freely accessible (open data)
- Listening to and involvement of citizens

7. Are there other actions, in addition to those listed above, that could contribute to achieving the objective (*insert/cite the first objective by priority*)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

7a. If the answer is yes:

Can you briefly tell us which ones?

Free answer

8. We list some actions below. How much would each contribute to achieving the objective (*insert/cite the second objective by priority*)?

Answers: Very much, Much, Partially, A little, Not at all, I don't know

- Results and solutions from public research
- Results and solutions from innovation through private companies
- Results and solutions from public research in collaboration with private companies
- Better public services (social services, mobility services, etc.)
- Better regional public policies (laws, sanctions, incentives)
- Better national or international public policies
- Change in people's behaviour and lifestyle
- Reliable public information
- Data from public institutions, which are reliable and freely accessible (open data)
- Listening to and involvement of citizens

9. Are there other actions, in addition to those listed above, that could contribute to achieving the objective (*insert/cite the second objective by priority*)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

9a. If the answer is yes:

Can you briefly tell us which ones?

Free answer

SECTION III. LOMBARDY CITIZENS' NEEDS

10. Now we will talk about your personal/family context. We list below some needs. For each of them, please tell us if you feel they are important for you and/or your family.

Answers: Yes, No, I don't know

- Quality food in sufficient quantities
- Preventing diseases
- Receiving timely and appropriate care close to home
- Receiving care or rehabilitation at home, when possible
- Stimulating personal flourishing through culture and art
- Communicating efficiently with personal or school or work contacts
- Access to quality information
- Having user-friendly citizen services (e.g., registry office, school enrolment, medical booking)
- Moving on safe roads (as a pedestrian, cyclist, or motorist)
- Using efficient and non-polluting public transport
- Living in safe environments
- Living well among different cultures (multiculturalism)
- Ensuring the protection and inclusion in society of minorities and fragile persons (e.g., the disabled)
- Combating violence against women, homosexuals, and transgender people (gender-based violence)
- Working safely and with a decent salary

11. Are there any other needs you would add?

Answers: Yes, No

If the answer is "Yes":

11.a Can you briefly describe one of them?

Free answer

12. Among the needs you consider important for your personal/family context, please select the two most important.

Please mention the options with a "Yes" answer from question 10.

13. In your opinion, can research and innovation provide answers to the need (please mention the first need selected in question 12)?

Answers: Yes, Partially, No, I don't know

If the answer is "Yes":

13.a Can you explain how? Please indicate only one answer.

- By increasing the level of knowledge and understanding to respond to that need
- By providing concrete answers and/or solutions to that need
- By providing data and information that can be useful for policymakers
- By attracting both public and private investment and resources to meet that need
- Other (specify)

If the answer is "Partially" or "No":

13.b Can you explain why? Please indicate only one answer.

- Because research and innovation have nothing to do with this need
- Because a technological response alone would not fully solve the problem
- Because meeting the need requires better public services (social services, mobility services, etc.)
- Because responding to the need requires better public policies (e.g., laws, strategic plans, sanctions, incentives)
- Because responding to the need requires better citizens' behaviours and/or lifestyles
- Other (specify)

14. In your opinion, can research and innovation provide answers to the need (please mention the second need selected in question 12)?

Answers: Yes, Partially, No, I don't know

If the answer is "Yes":

14.a Can you explain how? Please indicate only one answer.

- By increasing the level of knowledge and understanding to respond to that need
- By providing concrete answers and/or solutions to that need
- By providing data and information that can be useful for policymakers
- By attracting both public and private investment and resources to meet that need
- Other (specify)

If the answer is “Partially” or “No”:

14.b Can you explain why? Please indicate only one answer.

- Because research and innovation have nothing to do with this need
- Because a technological response alone would not fully solve the problem
- Because meeting the need requires better public services (social services, mobility services, etc.)
- Because responding to the need requires better public policies (e.g., laws, strategic plans, sanctions, incentives)
- Because responding to the need requires better citizens’ behaviour and/or lifestyle
- Other (specify)

SECTION IV. DESIGNING RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PRIORITIES IN LOMBARDY

15. Here below you can find a list of options. With whom should the Lombardy Region dialogue to define on what research and innovation sectors invest and design targeted public policies (i.e., define research and innovation priorities)?

Answers (there is no limit on the number of choices):

- Citizens
- Universities and research centres
- Companies
- Third sector (e.g., associations, foundations, non-profit/not-for-profit organisations)
- Professional associations and scientific societies
- Citizens’ associations (e.g., consumer associations, rights associations, environmental associations, etc.)
- Municipalities
- National government
- European Union
- Other Italian Regions

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